

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF METAL CHELATES. PART I. ALUMINIUM SULPHOSALICYLATE

By R. K. NANDA AND S. ADITYA

The dissociation constant of the aluminium sulphosalicylate chelate has been determined at p_H 2.4, at different ionic strengths, by displacement method. The average value at the ionic strength 0.02, 0.05 and 0.2 are 1.72×10^{-5} , 1.94×10^{-5} and 2.58×10^{-5} respectively. The dissociation constant of the ferric sulphosalicylate chelate has also been determined at the same p_H . At ionic strength 0.02, 0.05 and 0.2 the average values are 1.14×10^{-5} , 1.39×10^{-5} and 1.57×10^{-5} respectively. The molar extinction coefficient of ferric sulphosalicylate chelate at 500 $m\mu$ has been determined and is 2036.

Aluminium is known to form complexes with many hydroxy-acids. More recently Lasater and Anderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1429) have studied the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex spectrophotometrically by the displacement method. They have used the coloured copper sulphosalicylate complex as the indicator and from the shift obtained in optical density, on adding aluminium perchlorate solution, have determined the molecular composition as also the dissociation constant of the aluminium complex. It is true, as reported by them, that the ferric sulphosalicylate complex cannot be suitably used as indicator for the determination of the molecular composition of the aluminium complex by Job's method, as no appreciable shift is obtained at comparable concentrations of iron and aluminium. But from the dissociation constants reported by Foley and Anderson (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 1195) for the ferric sulphosalicylate complex and that for the aluminium complex by Lasater and Anderson (*loc. cit.*), a measurable shift was to be expected, provided that sufficient aluminium ions were present in the system. In the present work the dissociation constant of the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex has been determined, assuming the complex to be of the (1:1) type, at different ionic strengths, using iron sulphosalicylate as the indicator, at p_H 2.4. The dissociation constant of the ferric sulphosalicylate complex had also to be determined at different ionic strengths as such data were not available in literature. Incidentally, the extinction coefficient of the ferric complex has also been determined at 500 $m\mu$ and at p_H 2.4.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving the reagent grade iron powder in perchloric acid and then oxidising with hydrogen peroxide. The excess hydrogen peroxide was destroyed by heating over a water-bath. Aluminium perchlorate was prepared by adding equivalent amounts of barium perchlorate and aluminium sulphate solutions. Aluminium, in the solution of aluminium perchlorate, thus obtained, was estimated, weighing as oxide. Reagent grade sulphosalicylic acid was used and the stock solution was standardised against a standard NaOH solution.

AlF₃ measurements of optical densities were taken with a Hilger 'UVISPEK' model H 700/303, spectrophotometer using a quartz prism. Matched glass cells of 10 mm light path were always used. The slit width was always 0.02 mm. Measurements were taken at room temperature ranging between 25° and 30°. In this connection it may be mentioned that Turner and Anderson (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 913) measured the optical density of copper sulphosalicylate complex at 22°, 25°, 27° and 30° and reported that the optical densities were within experimental error. So in the present work the optical densities were taken to be independent of temperature, over the range of variation of room temperature. Optical densities were measured at 500 m μ ; p_H measurements were made with a Marconi p_H -meter, model 1F 511 D.

TABLE I

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Conc. of NaClO ₄	Total molar concentration of Fe ³⁺	Sulphosalicylic acid.	Al ³⁺	Optical density of the soln.	$K_{Fe} \times 10^5$		$K_{Al} \times 10^3$	
0.02	0.0002	0.00018	...	0.306	0.98		...	
"	0.0002	0.00018	0.002	0.276	...		1.54	
"	0.0002	0.00018	0.004	0.253	...		2.00	
"	0.00028	0.0002	...	0.365	1.16		...	
"	0.00028	0.0002	0.002	0.337	...	Av	1.81	Av. 1.72
"	0.00028	0.0002	0.004	0.315	...		1.78	
"	0.0004	0.0002	...	0.384	1.27		...	
"	0.0004	0.0002	0.004	0.347	...		1.59	
"	0.0004	0.0002	0.006	0.332	...		1.60	
0.05	0.0002	0.00018	...	0.299	1.19		...	
"	0.0002	0.00018	0.002	0.267	...		2.23	
"	0.0002	0.00018	0.004	0.246	...		2.22	
"	0.00028	0.0002	...	0.358	1.43		...	
"	0.00028	0.0002	0.002	0.325	...		1.67	
"	0.00028	0.0002	0.004	0.310	...	"	2.12	" 1.94
"	0.00032	0.0002	...	0.319	1.35		...	
"	0.00032	0.0002	0.0032	0.327	...		1.76	
"	0.00032	0.0002	0.0048	0.316	...		1.98	
"	0.0004	0.0002	...	0.379	1.60		...	
"	0.0004	0.0002	0.004	0.339	...		1.68	
"	0.0004	0.0002	0.006	0.326	...		1.82	
0.2	0.0002021	0.0001821	...	0.294	1.51		...	
"	0.0002021	0.0001821	0.002	0.268	...		2.73	
"	0.0002021	0.0001821	0.004	0.251	...		2.75	
"	0.000283	0.0002023	...	0.360	1.57		...	
"	0.000283	0.0002023	0.002	0.334	...	"	2.57	" 2.58
"	0.000283	0.0002023	0.004	0.315	...		2.62	
"	0.0004042	0.0002023	...	0.383	1.63		...	
"	0.0004042	0.0002023	0.004	0.349	...		2.37	
"	0.0004042	0.0002023	0.005	0.336	...		2.44	

For the determination of the dissociation constant of the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex, different amounts of ferric perchlorate (0.002M), sulphosalicylic acid (0.002M) and aluminium perchlorate were mixed. The required amounts of sodium perchlorate to adjust the ionic strength and perchloric acid or NaOH to adjust the p_H to 2.4, when diluted, were added and the mixture diluted to 50 c.c. in each case with distilled water. Simultaneously a 'blank' solution was prepared by mixing the same amounts of ferric perchlorate and sulphosalicylic acid as in the previous ones, but without aluminium perchlorate. The p_H and ionic strength of this mixture were also adjusted to the same values as in the previous ones. From the optical densities of these mixtures, the dissociation constants of the ferric and aluminium complexes were calculated.

The extinction coefficient of the ferric complex was also determined at different ionic strengths by measuring the optical densities of the solutions in which the ratio of $[Fe^{3+}]$ to [sulphosalicylate] was 1:8 or 1:9 and *vice versa*. As expected, the ionic strength was found to have no effect upon the extinction coefficient, the average value of which came out to be 2035. It may be noted that the value reported by Foley and Anderson (*loc. cit.*) for the extinction coefficient of the complex at p_H 2.38 was 753, but from their curves the value of extinction coefficient on calculation came to ~ 2000 .

DISCUSSION

Taking the extinction coefficient of ferric sulphosalicylate to be equal to 2036, the dissociation constant of the ferric complex has been calculated at various ionic strengths. These are recorded in column 6 of the table and the average values in column 7. It may be interesting to compare our values with those of Foley and Anderson (*loc. cit.*). They obtained a value of $1.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5}$ for the dissociation constant of the complex at p_H 2.38 and ionic strength of about 0.06, whereas in the present investigation at $\mu=0.05$ and $p_H=2.4$, the average value obtained was 1.39×10^{-5} . In view of the experimental limitations the agreement is good. The values of dissociation constant show a trend to increase with ionic strength.

We have assumed the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex to be of the 1:1 type, as Job's method cannot be applied under the present experimental conditions. Such an assumption seems to be justified in view of the identical ferric complex formed under similar conditions. Also Lasater and Anderson (*loc. cit.*) have found the aluminium complex to be of the 1:1 type at p_H 4.0, and at p_H 2.4 the formation of higher complex, i. e. (1:2), is least probable. So the dissociation constant of the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex has been calculated, taking it to be of the 1:1 type. The dissociation constants at different ionic strengths are shown in column 8 and the average values at each ionic strength, in column 9 of the table. Here also it is found that the dissociation constants increase with ionic strength. The value of the dissociation constant of the same complex, reported by the previous workers, is about 5×10^{-4} . The comparison of this value with ours became difficult as these workers did not record the ionic strength. But on the average, our values are about four times higher. This difference may be ascribed to the following factors. Firstly, Anderson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have worked with

copper sulphate solution. In a recent communication Monk *et al.* (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 816) have reported the dissociation constant of CuSO_4 to be 4.5×10^{-3} (5×10^{-3}), which is almost of the same order as that reported for the aluminium sulphosalicylate complex. The presence of sulphate ions might have vitiated their results.

Anderson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) worked at p_H 4, whereas the present work was carried out at p_H 2.4. This difference in p_H might also be the cause of the difference noted. It may be pointed out at this stage that due to the hydrolysis of ferric perchlorate, ferric sulphosalicylate could not be used as indicator for the displacement measurements at p_H 4.

Further, as mentioned earlier, they have not recorded the ionic strength of the solution. It is probable that a large difference in the ionic strength might bring about the difference observed. Apparently the best check would be to determine the nature as also the dissociation constant of the complex from measurements in the ultraviolet at the desired p_H and ionic strength. Work along this line is already in progress for the aluminium sulphosalicylate and such other complexes.

The authors express their thanks to Dr. B. Prasad for his interest in the work.

MAJURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHEW COLLEGE, CUTTACK-3

Received March 2, 1957.